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DRUG UTILIZATION PATTERN OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS IN A TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL IN DAVANGERE

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ABSTRACT

Objective The study was carried out with the aim to understand the drug utilization pattern of antihypertensive drugs in the medicine wards of a tertiary care teaching hospital. The secondary objective of the study is to determine the average number of Anti-Hypertensive drugs per prescription, To assess the prescribing pattern of anti-hypertensive's according to age(according to JNC guidelines).Category-wise distribution of drugs. A retro- prospective observational study was conducted at SSIMS & RC, Davangere, Karnataka for a period of six months **Methodology** Total of 100 patients were included in the study.The collected data include patient's information's on demography, drug therapy and length of hospital stay. Antihypertensive drug utilization was measured in terms of DDD/100 bed days. Results 52 males and 48 females were identified in the study. Calcium channel blockers were the most commonly prescribed drug class. Amlodipine was the most consumed drug in the wards (DDD/100 bed-days).The majority of the patients (32%) were in the age group of 60-69 years. **Conclusion:** The increased prescription of calcium channel blockers than diuretics shows that the prescribing pattern is in line with the recommendations of JNC VIII GUIDELINES (2014 Hypertension Guideline). Evaluation of utilization of anti-hypertensive agents and implementation of effective strategies can greatly aid in improving the quality use of anti-hypertensive agents.

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INTRODUCTION

Worldwide the estimates for prevalence of hypertension, to a large extent as 1 billion individuals and approximately around 7.1 million deaths per year may be attributable to hypertension (JNC 7, 2003). Hypertension is one of the leading contributing factor to many other diseases including Myocardial Infarction (MI), stroke, heart failure, renal failure and retinopathy, a leading cause of death also. In 2004, an estimated 55,000 deaths were directly attributable to hypertension and it was also considered as an underlying cause in other 300,000 deaths (Rosamond et al., 2008). [1]

Drug utilization is defined by WHO as “the marketing, distribution, prescription, and use of drugs in a society, with special emphasis on the resulting medical, social and economic consequences” [2] Regular evaluation of the antihypertensive prescribing patterns are essential these days due to the growing epidemic of hypertension, increasing number of new antihypertensive drugs and the increasing number of drug combinations that are introduced into the market each year together with alteration in guidelines. Correct diagnosis, accurate prescribing, proper dispensing, appropriate packing and good patient counselling are the important criteria for rational use of drugs [3, 9]. Also the use of multiple drugs not only facilitates the cost and regimens complication but also increases the incidence of undesirable drug reactions and drug interactions [10]. The risk factors for CVDs are multiple such as elevated cholesterol and blood pressure levels, excessive smoking habits, diabetes, malnutrition and fatness etc. [11].

JNC VIII GUIDELINES (2014 Hypertension Guideline) [12].

GUIDELINES	POPULATION	goal bp, mmHg	INITIAL DRUGS TREATMENT OPTION
JNCVIII:2014 HYPERTENSION GUIDELINE	GENERAL ≥60 Y	<150/90 mmHg	NONBLACK: CCB, ACEI, ARB, THIAZIDE-TYPE DIURETIC. BLACK: CCB OR THIAZIDE-TYPE DIURETIC.
	GENERAL <60 Y	<140/90 mmHg	
	DIABETES	<140/90 mmHg	
	CKD	<140/90 mmHg	ACEI OR ARB

OBJECTIVES

The study was carried out with the aim to understand the drug utilization pattern of antihypertensive drugs in the medicine wards of a tertiary care teaching hospital. The secondary objective of the study is to determine the average number of Anti-Hypertensive drugs per prescription, To assess the prescribing pattern of anti-hypertensive's according to age (according to JNC guidelines). Category-wise distribution of drugs. A retro- prospective observational study was conducted at SSIMS & RC, Davangere, Karnataka for a period of six months

MATERIALS AND METHODS

- STUDY SITE: Shamanur Shivashankarappa Institute of Medical Sciences and Research Centre (SSIMS & RC), Davangere.
- DURATION OF STUDY: Study were conducted for a period of six months
- SAMPLE SIZE: 100 SUBJECTS
- STUDY DESIGN: A retro- prospective observational study.
- SOURCE OF DATA: The data about patients were collected from in-patients case sheets of MEDICINE UNIT in a tertiary care teaching hospital.
- INCLUSION CRITERIA: All in-patients above 30 years who were admitted in medicine ward and diagnosed with Hypertension of both gender
- EXCLUSION CRITERIA:
 - Patients suffering from hypertension with co-morbid conditions were excluded in the study
 - Patients on ventilators or seriously ill patients requiring ICU admission.
 - Patients unwilling to participate.
 - All outpatients coming in OPD
- STATISTICAL METHOD: Simple percentage calculations were used and expressed using graphs. Approval was obtained from Institutional Ethics Committee before initiating the study on 17th September 2016 and ethical clearance certificate reference number is IEC/ 32/16-17/ BPC.

METHOD OF COLLECTION OF DATA:

- The study was carried out by regular visits to various in-patient departments to collect case sheets from patients above 30 years of age.
- The relevant data collected from case sheet were properly documented.

The DDD/100 bed-days of the antihypertensive drugs were calculated to find the antihypertensive consumption in the medical wards.

The DDD/100 bed-days were calculated by the formula [8]:

DDD/100 bed-days = No. of units administered in the study period (mg) x 100

DDD (mg) x no. of days in study period x no. of beds x bed occupancy

RESULTS:

During the 6 months period of study 160 prescriptions for Hypertension were analyzed and the prescriptions with exclusion criteria were excluded, and the sample size was 100. Out of 100 patients who were prescribed with antihypertensive drugs during the study period, 52 patients were males and 48 were females. Maximum patients belonged to age group of 60-69 years (32%), followed by 50-59 years (26%), 70-79 years (20%), 40-49 years (13%), 30-39 years (5%), 80-89 years (3%), and above 90 years (1%).

TABLE 1: SOCIAL HABITS AMONG THE ENROLLED PATIENTS.

CONDITIONS	NUMBER OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
NEWLY DIAGNOSED HTN CASES	45	45%
KNOWN CASE OF HTN	55	55%
FAMILY HISTORY OF HYPERTENSION	38	38%
ALCOHOLICS	36	36%
NON ALCOHOLICS	64	64%
SMOKERS	73	73%
NON SMOKERS	27	27%

Out of 100 patient 55% were known case of hypertension and 45% were newly diagnosed cases of hypertension. Preliminary study revealed the presence of alcoholism and smoking such that 25% were alcoholics and 27% were smokers and 38% had a strong history of hypertension in their family.

TABLE NO 2: DISTRIBUTION OF PATIENTS IN DIFFERENT STAGES OF HYPERTENSION.

STAGES OF HYPERTENSION	NUMBER OF PATIENTS N=100	PERCENTAGE (%)
PRE-HYPERTENSION	5	5
STAGE-1	59	59
STAGE-2	36	36

The patients were categorized depending on the stages of the hypertension that they met. 5% patients belonged to pre-hypertension stage, 59% patients belonged to stage 1 hypertension and 36% patients belonged to stage 2 hypertension.

TABLE 3: DISTRIBUTION OF DRUG THERAPY USAGE PATTERN.

DRUG THERAPY	GENDER	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE
MONOTHERAPY	MALE	18	47.36
	FEMALE	20	52.64
N=38/100			
COMBINATION	MALE	34	54.84
THERAPY	FEMALE	28	45.16
N=62/100			

We categorized the patients on gender basics to study the type of drug therapy they received. Out of 52 male patients 34.62% received monotherapy and 65.4% received combination therapy. Similarly out of 48 female patients 41.6% received monotherapy and 58.4% received combination therapy.

TABLE 4: CLASS OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS USED IN PERCENTAGE.

CLASS OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS	PERCENTAGE OF DRUGS PRESCRIBED BY CLASS(%)
Calcium channel blockers	53
Angiotensin receptor blocker	23
Diuretics	10
Beta blocker	6
Alpha + beta blocker	4
Angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitor	3
Centrally acting	1
TOTAL	100

During the study period, the most frequently prescribed drug among both monotherapy and combination therapy was Calcium Channel Blockers (CCBs) 53%, Angiotensin Receptor Blockers (ARBs) 23%, Diuretics (10%) Beta blockers (6%), ALPHA+BETA BLOCKER 4% ACE Inhibitors 3% and Centrally Acting Agents (CAAs) 1%.

TABLE NO 5: CLASSES OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS PRESCRIBED AS MONOTHERAPY.

CLASS	FREQUENCY OF PRESCRIBING	PERCENTAGE(%)
CCBS	12	31.5
ARBS	9	23.6
BETA BLOEKRS	8	21.2
ACEIS	4	10.5
DIURETICS	2	5.3
AABS	2	5.3
CAAS	1	2.6
TOTAL	38	100

Out of 38 monotherapy prescriptions the most frequently prescribed drug was Calcium Channel Blockers (CCBs) 31.5%, Angiotensin Receptor Blockers (ARBs) 23.6%, Beta blockers (21.2%), ACE Inhibitors (10.5%), Diuretics (5.3%), Alpha Adrenergic Blocker (AABs) 5.3% and Centrally Acting Agents (CAAs) 2.6%.

TABLE 6: CLASSES OF ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUGS PRESCRIBED AS COMBINATION THERAPY.

CLASS	FREQUENCY OF PRESCRIBING	PERCENTAGE(%)
ARB+DIURETIC	21	33.8
CCB+ B BLOCKER	20	32.2
DIURETIC+DIURETIC	8	12.9
ARB+CCB	6	9.6
ACEI+DIURETIC	4	6.7
CCB+DIURETIC	3	4.8
TOTAL	62	100

We also observed few combination drugs in the prescription, Drug combinations were categorized depending on their class. The most frequently prescribed drugs combinations out of 62 drug combination given ARB+Diuretics (33.8%), CCB+betablocker (32.2%), Diuretic+Diuretic (12.9%), ARB+CCB (9.6%), ACEI+Diuretic (6.7%) and CCB+Diuretic (4.8%).

TABLE 7: ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUG CONSUMPTION IN GENERAL MEDICINE WARDS.

DRUG NAME	ATC CODE	DDD(mg)	DDD/100 BED-DAYS
AMLODIPINE	C08CA01	5	38
FELODIPINE	C08CA902	5	1.10
CLINIDIPINE	C08CA14	10	2.03
NIFEDIPINE	C08CA05	30	2.5
LOSARTAN	C09CA01	50	7.2
VALSARTAN	C09CA03	80	2.1
OLMESARTAN	C09CA08	20	1.1
TELMISARTAN	C09CA07	40	4.2
FRUSEMIDE	C03CA01	40	3.1
TORSEMIDE	C03CA04	15	2.5
MANNITOL	R05CB16	0.8	1.5
HYDROCHLOROTHIAZIDE	C03AB03	25	2.8
ATENOLOL	C07AB03	75	4.2
METOPROLOL	C07AB02	0.15	1.2
PROPRANOLOL	C07AA05	0.16	1.5
CLONIDINE	C02AC01	0.45	1.2
RAMIPRIL	C09AA05	2.5	1.4
CARVEDILOL	C07AG02	37.5	1.4
TOTAL ANTIHYPERTENSIVE DRUG CONSUMPTION			79.03

The antihypertensive drug consumption in general medicine wards was calculated in terms of DDD/100 bed-days. The average occupancy index was 0.85. During the study period, Amlodipine was the most prescribed antihypertensive drug with a value of 38 DDD/100 bed days followed by Losartan, with 7.2 DDD/100 bed-days. Total antihypertensive drug consumption was found to be 79.03 DDD/100 bed-days. The ATC code and DDD/100 bed-days of respective antihypertensive drugs were mentioned in the below table.

TABLE NO 8 NUMBER OF CALCIUM CHANNEL BLOCKERS GIVEN.

DRUGS	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE(%)
FELODIPINE	3	5.6
CLINIDIPINE	8	15.09
NIFEDIPINE	9	16.98
AMLODIPINE	33	62.33
TOTAL	53	100

Among 53% calcium channel blockers, most used drug was Amlodipine (62.33%) followed by Nifedipine (16.98%) , Clinidipine (15.09%) and Felodipine(5.6%).

TABLE NO 9: NUMBER OF ANGIOTENSIN RECEPTOR BLOCKERS GIVEN.

DRUGS	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE(%)
VALSARTAN	1	4.34
OLMESARTAN	2	8.69
LOSARTAN	5	21.73
TEMISARTAN	15	65.23
TOTAL	23	100

Among Angiotensin receptor blockers (23%) most used drug was Telmisartan (65.23%) followed by Losartan(21.73%) and Olmesartan(4.34%).

TABLE NO 10: NUMBER OF DIURETICS GIVEN.

CLASS OF DRUGS	DRUGS	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE
LOOP DIURETICS	FUROSEMIDE	6	60
	TORSEMIDE	2	20
OSMOTIC DIURETICS	MANNITOL	1	10
THIAZIDE DIURETICS	HYDROCHLORTHIAZIDE	1	10
TOTAL		10	100

Among (10%) diuretics given most used drug was loop diuretics (80%) followed by osmotic diuretics (10%) and thiazide diuretics(10%).

TABLE NO 11 : NUMBER OF BETA BLOCKERS GIVEN:

DRUGS	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE(%)
PROPRANALOL	1	16.66
METOPROLOL	2	33.37
ATENOLOL	3	50
TOTAL	6	100

Among(6%) beta receptor blockers, mostly used drug was atenolol(75%) followed by Metoprolol(33.37%) and Propranolol (16.66%).

TABLE NO:12 NUMBER OF OTHER DRUGS GIVEN.

CLASS OF DRUGS	DRUGS	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE(%)
ALPHA+BETA BLOCKERS	CAEVEDILOL	4	40
ACE INHIBITORS	RAMIPRIL	3	30
CENTRALLY ACTING	CLONIDINE	1	10
TOTAL		8	100

Among the other drugs given the most used drug class were alpha+beta blockers (4%) and ACE inhibitors (3%) then centrally acting drugs (1%).

DISCUSSION

A prescription based assessment is considered to be one of the most effective methods to measure and estimate drug utilization and dispensing practice of pharmacist. It is also important to assess the rational usage of drugs.

Male patients were predominant in the present study. They were noticed to have the habits of either smoking or alcoholism or both, which is one of the most contributing factors for hypertension. The mean age of the patients was in between the age 60-69 years and it was almost similar to the study reports of Juno J. Joel that shows the mean age of 60.7 ± 11.72 years [4].

The present study shows that 62% of patients were stable with combination therapy and the rest of the patients with monotherapy. The same observation was noticed in the study conducted by P. Sujatha [5] combination therapy was mostly given among geriatrics and non-geriatrics patients than monotherapies. In this study among monotherapy, calcium channel blockers (31.5%) and angiotensin receptor blockers (23.6%) were the most prescribed. The results are similar to a study conducted by Juno J. Joel where calcium channel blockers (48.2%) followed by angiotensin receptor blockers (19.4%) are highly utilized.

Among combination drug therapy, diuretic with angiotensin receptor blocker (33.8%) and calcium channel blocker with beta blocker (32.2%) were the most commonly prescribed drugs. The results are in conformity to the study conducted by Juno J. Joel where diuretic with angiotensin receptor blocker (22.9%) and beta blocker with calcium channel blocker (21.3%) were the most commonly prescribed combinations [4]. The results are in conformity to the study conducted by An and Kale where diuretic with angiotensin receptor blocker (29.5%) and beta blocker with calcium channel blocker (22.1%) were the most commonly prescribed combinations [6].

The antihypertensive medicine consumption in the wards was calculated in terms of DDD/100 bed-days. The most utilized drugs in the general medicine wards were Amlodipine with 38 DDD/100 bed-days. A similar observation is seen in a study conducted by Juno J. Joel et al. where the consumption of amlodipine in the wards was 32 DDD/100 bed-days [4]. Total antihypertensive drug consumption in the medicine wards were 79.03 DDD/100 bed-days. A similar observation was also seen in a study conducted by Jhaveri BN et al. where the consumption of amlodipine in the wards was 29 DDD/100 bed-days [7].

CONCLUSION

The treatment of Hypertension keeps changing and newer drugs are being added at a rapid pace. It is recommended that regular continuing education should be provided to prescribers on rational use of drugs in Hypertension and comorbid conditions. According to recommendations made by the JNC 8 guidelines, first line drugs for the management of hypertension can be any one of the four drug classes like calcium channel blockers, angiotensin receptor blockers, angiotensin converting enzyme inhibitors and diuretics. The increased prescription of calcium channel blockers than diuretics shows that the prescribing pattern is in line with the recommendations. In our study, Amlodipine consumption in the medical wards was found to be high when compared with other drugs.

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REFERENCES

1. F.Zafar, H.Ali ,S. Naveed ,O.U. Korai ,M. Rizvi , G.R.Naqvi,S.Siddiqui.Drug Utilization Pattern in Cardiovascular Diseases: A Descriptive Study in Tertiary Care Settings in Pakistan .J Bioequiv Availab 2015; 7:1
2. J.JohanPandian,K. Manimekalai,R.Velvizhy . Pattern of antihypertensive drug utilization in a tertiary care hospital. int j pharm bio sci 2015 oct; 6(4): (p) 759 - 764
3. Krishna Murti . Prescription Pattern of Anti-Hypertensive Drugs in Adherence to JNC- 7 Guidelines. American Journal of Pharmacology and Toxicology 2015; 10 (1): 27.31
4. J.Juno Joel, N.Daniel , R.C.S Sharma,C.S. Shastry. Drug utilization pattern of antihypertensive drugs in a tertiary care hospital in south India. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences 2014; 3(10):1094-1099
5. P.Sujatha .Drug utilization pattern of antihypertensive drugs in geriatric and non-geriatric population in a tertiary care government hospital srikakulam. j of evolution of med and dent sci. feb 12, 2015;4(13) 2278-4802
6. Kale A, Maniyar YA, Kale A. Prescribing Patterns of Antihypertensive Drugs in A Tertiary Care Hospital. Sch Acad J Pharm, 2013; 2(5): 416–418
7. Jhaveri BN, Patel TK, Barvaliya MJ, Tripathi CB. Drug utilization pattern and pharmacoeconomic analysis in geriatric medical in-patients of a tertiary care hospital of India. J Pharmacol Pharmacother, 2014;5:15-20
8. WHO Collaborating Centre for Drug Statistics Methodology. Guidelines for ATC classification and DDD assignment. 14th ed. Oslo (Norway): World Health Organization, 2011:14-30
9. Sreedevi K, Venkateswara Rao J, Fareedullah Md, Vijayakumar S (2011) A study on prescription pattern of statins in cardiovascular disease. Der Pharmacia Lettre, 3: 393-396
10. Taskeen M, Anitha N, Ali SR, Bharath R, Khan AB (2012) A study on rational drug prescribing pattern in geriatric patients in Hyderabad metropolitan. JDDTJ 2: 109-113
11. Manjula DAS, Sriram S, Rajalingam B, Anthraper AR, Varghese RS, et al. (2012) Evaluation of the Rationality of Fixed Dose Combinations of Cardiovascular drugs in a Multispecialty Tertiary care hospital in Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India. Hygeia. J D Med 4: 51-58
12. James PA, Oparil S, Carter BL, Eighth Joint National Committee (JNC 8) Members, et al. 2014 evidence-based guideline for the management of high blood pressure in adults: report from the panel members appointed to the Eighth Joint National Committee (JNC 8), Supplemental Content. JAMA. 2014; 311:507–20.

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